

The ARDC Community Data Lab architecture

Research software deployment principles and patterns for integrity, reproducibility and sustainability

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Scope

This article sets out a principles-driven architectural pattern for research software infrastructure and architecture for the ARDC Community Data Lab (CDL). The architecture is in line with the CARE and FAIR principles and with an emphasis on sustainability.

The CDL is summarised [on the project web page](#):

The ARDC Community Data Lab will enable the sharing of an increasing range of tools and datasets, provide environments for running the tools, and options for researchers to analyse and annotate datasets. It will be a platform that not only shares a number of instruments and infrastructures, but also provides governance and procedures that have protocols, and practices for managing and recording research as a process.

The ARDC Community Data Lab will facilitate cross-institutional collaboration, enabling researchers to work collaboratively in groups and conduct open research.

For more information about the CDL see the [Phase 1 project plan](#) and the [proposed architecture document entering into the first phase of the CDL \(Sefton, 2023\)](#), which discussed how implementation of the FAIR principles could be supported by technical architecture.

The following issues are crucial to the CDL project but are outside the focus area for this architecture document:

- Researcher engagement and outreach
- Prioritising the order in which disciplines, tools and techniques get support
- Specific discussion of Phase 2 initial work packages.

Audience

This document is primarily aimed at the ARDC and its partners such as software developers engaged in technical implementation and researchers who work hands-on with code and data in the course of doing

their research. The principles here are important for a generalist research audience but we would expect that these will be translated as part of the engagement process for the CDL.

Current architecture: summary

The Community Data Lab phase 1 is an architecture modelled on the GLAM Workbench, maintained by Tim Sherratt. In this model, a series of web pages provide pathways for novice to advanced users to access a number of data sources, including many tools to use data from the National Library of Australia's Trove service.

The GLAM Workbench represents a particular kind of best practice in research infrastructure; it is largely built on static, declaratively specified web pages and code, in the form of Jupyter notebooks which reference archival repository services, mainly Trove. Each element of this infrastructure represents a FAIR Digital Object¹ (in the broad sense) that can be 'parked' in an appropriate repository (e.g., code can be deposited in Zenodo). This pattern has been dubbed "Infrastructure at Rest" by the ARDC's Tom Honeyman, a term we will use throughout this document. We discuss some alternative implementations below, including Neurodesk ([Renton et al., 2023](#)) which shares some of the same elements as CDL but a much higher maintenance burden.

¹ There is a [project to create a FAIR Digital Object framework](#) which proposes an entire new infrastructure for FAIR research, but the RO-Crate community is working to propose that an entire new infrastructure is not required and existing web infrastructure, repositories and identifier schemes can be used to implement FAIR research.

Web based guides, tutorials and manuals including executable code notebooks (based on the Glam Workbench) <<guidance>>		
Jupyter Notebooks Repository access code (eg Trove tools to create collections) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generic analytical building blocks • Geo-spatial analysis ('hotspots') • Integration – various proofs-of concept 	New Services <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annotation workbench • Experimental format-transforming proxies Legacy tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Voyant tools • Stylometric IA API/server app 	Code Development <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Version control (Github, Gilab etc) • Project management Github, gitlab, Jira etc) Execution environments: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NeCTAR Binderhub (and backup options) • BYOD download
<<workpaces>>		
Archival repositories		
Public (limited to OA), eg: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zenodo • Dryad • Figshare 	National discipline / domain <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trove • Language Data Commons of Australia • PROV 	Institutional (where available)
<<repository>>		

The above summary table uses the visual vocabulary established in the architecture document ([Sefton, 2023](#)) of phase 1, the three infrastructure “food groups”. (The term <<support>> (or support and training) was used in the original document, we have changed this to <<guidance>> to better capture the training that is key to this part of the infrastructure.

<<guidance>> and training	<<guidance>>
Workspaces	<<workspace>>
Archival Repositories	<<repository>>

The phase 1 architecture document also explains in some detail the patterns needed to support FAIR data; looking at infrastructures that need to be in place to support Findability and Accessibility of data, with detailed discussion of Reuse services. The links between FAIR data and the architectural ‘food groups’ are summarised in this table.

	FAIR Focus
Guidance	Findability of FAIR Research Objects including data and code
Workspaces	Reuse of data and code, Interoperability via use of Standards
Archival Repositories	Key services for Findability (indexes/catalogues build on archival repositories), long term stability of code and data for Reuse

Existing ARDC frameworks

An article by ARDC staff sets out 4 general principles for software solutions which would be familiar in any IT department, along the lines of “Buy don’t build”, and “and if you do build, build for re-use”: [\(Levett et al., 2022\)](#)

- **Access:** can the problem be solved by direct people to access existing appropriate FAIR-ready infrastructure? (i.e., deploy nothing – but do NOT encourage adoption of inappropriate solutions just because they are there)
- **Adopt:** can the problem be solved by deploying existing solutions (e.g., deploying an instance)?
- **Adapt:** can the problem be solved by adapting an existing solution to better fit the needs of possible users?
- **Abstract:** Is the problem a common pattern across differing needs when expressed more abstractly. If so, can a simpler, broader solution (or component) be proposed?

This article also says:

The authors believe that the FAIR principles should also be applied to platforms due to their key role in the digital infrastructures that store, manage, analyse, and share other research objects:

- **Continuity of the research record requires ongoing access to data**, and the ability to reproduce research results.
- Given the increasing volume and complexity of data, access to **software is essential** to support access and reproducibility.

- This software often is deployed through platforms, both for ease of use and to provide access to enabling underpinning infrastructure.
- These **platforms need to be sustained over the long term** to meet the continuity driver.

It is worth noting that this sustaining can occur in two ways. **One is the ongoing maintenance of platforms, so that they continue to meet the evolving needs of their target community of users.** In this case, re-use of platforms and their components leads to less wheel-reinvention, greater use of shared or re-used code and thus more sustainable platforms. The other is where the platform is not necessarily kept available as a maintained running instance but is **archived in a form (virtual machine image or container) that allows it to be “spun up”** as needed [NOTE: this is what we’re calling Infrastructure at Rest (IaR)], perhaps to reproduce results from a paper in the journal literature.

Obviously, the authors of *this* principles paper also believe that the FAIR principles should be applied to research infrastructure. In the CDL principles introduced below we have built on the general approach outlined by Levett et al to address the key concepts highlighted in bold above and take note of their general principles starting with the letter A.

This table puts these into context with the CDL, with **Access** and **Adopt** as the most important – the CDL is built for sustainability by reaching first for established infrastructure, and where new services are needed, making sure that it can be archived as Infrastructure at Rest.

Access	The ARDC is encouraging participants in the CDL to work at this end as much as possible. The goal is to use the extensive research specific and general purpose infrastructure that is already there, and adopt existing mainstream services such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Binderhub for flexible code execution. • Zenodo and other repositories for depositing (OA) data and code • Github as a workspace (though not an archival repository)
Adopt	
Adapt	This approach has been tried many times in ARDC partnerships: for instance, the Australian Imaging Service (AIS) federated platform adapted XNAT for their needs. They pushed the changes upstream, integrating with an existing project that has governance and development resources in place.
Abstract	For instance, for the burrows-zeta algorithm, which is one of the selling points of CDL phase 1 work around stylometrics (Stylometrics Intelligent Archive - SIA). To abstract the core of this we would find a library that handles word frequency and other basic text analytical methods, and add the burrow-zeta algorithm then re-create the SIA application as a series of notebooks (which may have simple point and click interfaces). See if the maintainers will take on the maintenance of the algorithm (admittedly, not always straightforward).

Emerging best-practice in software development and reuse

The original FAIR principles article calls for software code to be considered an output of, or input to, research that is treated in a similar way to publications and research data; it should be made available for the long term, and is accessible to those wanting to reproduce research findings and reuse analytical methods and data.

The goal is for **scholarly digital objects of all kinds** to become ‘first class citizens’ in the scientific publication ecosystem, where the quality of the publication—and more importantly, the impact of the publication—is a function of its ability to be accurately and appropriately found, re-used, and cited over time, by all stakeholders, both human and mechanical. <http://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

This is described in an EOSC report in terms of infrastructure:

"Software that researchers in any discipline may feel the need to have scholarly infrastructure support for, no matter if it is considered a tool, a result or an object of study"(Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission), 2020)

And the same article expands on the “scholarly digital objects of all kinds”²:

The elements of the FAIR Principles are related, but independent and separable. The Principles define characteristics that contemporary data resources, tools, vocabularies and infrastructures should exhibit to assist discovery and reuse by third-parties.

[...]

One such example is highly sensitive or personally-identifiable data, where publication of rich metadata to facilitate discovery, including clear rules regarding the process for accessing the data, provides a high degree of ‘FAIRness’ even in the absence of FAIR publication of the data itself. A second example involves the publication of non-data research objects. Analytical workflows, for example, are a critical component of the scholarly ecosystem, and their formal publication is necessary to achieve both transparency and scientific reproducibility. The FAIR principles can equally be applied to these non-data assets, which need to be identified, described, discovered, and reused in much the same manner as data.

The Software Sustainability Institute in the UK promoted the publication of software as a key part of the scholarly record, for example in this post from 2016, [Publish or be damned?](#). The Institute then promoted this for several years using the phrase "[Software as a first class citizen](#)".

For research workflows or analyses that can be captured as re-runnable source code this approach to creating Scholarly Digital Objects is now reasonably straightforward: code can be made available, and can be packaged in such a way that it represents infrastructure at rest. Well described objects can be “rehydrated” from a preserved state, to run in a standard execution environment. This includes fully open code stacks, as well as workflows that may include proprietary components.

“Well described” means that code is accompanied by manifests and metadata that allow an execution environment to be created and successfully launched – Binderhub itself implements this pattern for software dependencies, and work is proceeding on enhancing this so that hardware execution requirements can also be expressed – at time of writing the Language Data Commons of Australia with its partner AARNet is working on a CodeMeta compatible RO-Crate [metadata profile](#) for this.

In contrast, encouraging the saving of execution state ‘baked in’ to a virtual machine (or a container image) means that code workflows may NOT be re-composable and easily updated; having a detailed ‘recipe’ rather than just the baked goods maximises the chances of being able to reuse software over the long term.

² The term “FAIR Digital Object” emerged later, and was originally associated with an attempt to invent an entire new set of protocols and infrastructure for object exchange. The RO-Crate community has engaged vigorously with the FDO group to advocate for the use of existing protocols such as HTTP and established linked-data approaches.

These workflows typically have the following attributes:

1. **A clear separation between data (including metadata) and code** (as opposed to, say an Excel file containing a mixture of data and formulae). Code can reference data drawn from existing repositories or newly sourced data that is still being worked on.
2. “Literate” Code that runs in an execution environment; **a command line on a personal or shared computer, notebook, or workflow engine environment** (Workflow engines have not featured much in CDL discussions but are widely used in STEM environments, and range from online environments such as Galaxy to to command line systems that may run in High Performance Computing (HPC) or cloud environments).
3. **Analytical software that is openly or accessibly licensed** (even though it may run in a proprietary execution environment (eg Matlab)
4. A maturity pattern (we have dubbed this **librification**) where software moves from individual instances of code that implements an analytical process or algorithm to software **libraries** that can be used to assemble or contrast analytical processes. Taking Notebooks as an example, there is a maturity ladder from a string of code blocks, to named functions, to testing those named functions (see (Pimentel et al., 2019)), to publishing the functions themselves as reusable libraries. Note that this point is made in the context of computational code; notebooks designed to develop skills or illustrate concepts may not be as abstracted.
5. **Virtualisation of execution environments**; in the last decade potential for software reuse has improved dramatically with the availability of containers, including Singularity (research focussed) and Docker (which is general computing infrastructure). This allows previously precarious software stacks to be captured in full. Also helpful are whole-of-machine virtualization and hardware emulation environments which can capture GUI-based interactive computing tools (but with attendant problems mentioned above with reproducing settings).

In the context of the Community Data Lab, the Trove Data Guide which builds on the existing GLAM Workbench has all these attributes, it provides code and data separation and allows for execution in a variety of notebooks, and its analytical tools are by default available as open source. This approach follows the four A principles above in that it **Accesses** existing infrastructure, including standard services such as online git repositories, static web pages and binderhub implementations. It **adopts** existing code in the form of libraries, and provides a platform for **Adaptation**, and the approach uses **abstractions** such as software libraries which capture the ‘intellectual core’ of analytical processes in a reusable way via software **libraries**. Code can be executed in Binderhub at the click of a button.

Annotation-based workflows

Ian McCrabb says in a comment on a draft of this CDL architecture:

If I was asked to abstract the digital in our own research projects, it would be ‘relationship graphing’. We do incremental, cumulative, granular, and collaborative semantic annotation and linking of heterogeneous content and data. Rather than follow a research paradigm of repeatable experiments (text set-algorithm-result set) we *build node graphs* as a research output. Albeit a little glib, this ‘relationship graphing’ characterisation might be applied across a range of projects.

Classic Humanities scholarship actually follows this mode, a book or paper IS in a sense a node-graph of text nodes which reference other resources be they primary materials or other annotations (or at least a cluster).

This is articulating a research pattern which has been implemented in software a number of times, one of the most common of these is that research projects often create a website which explores the research domain with data typically embedded in the application. This table lists some of the common tools:

Specific linked-data-like approaches	OHRM, Heurist, Omeka (Classic and “S”), Huni, Nodegoat, IIIF, Keeping Culture, Crate-O
General purpose	Wordpress, Drupal etc
Ad hoc	LAMP-stack developments, often using technologies which spike in popularity then dramatically decline (Zope, Ruby on Rails)

Some of these systems exist in a linked data ecosystem (notably the linked-data approaches).

Public Infrastructure (often used to reconcile reference IDs, terms)	Wikidata ³ , ARDC Vocabulary Services, PURL, ARK IDs. DOI
Linked-data based standards	IIIF, RO-Crate

There have been two projects under the HASS and Indigenous Data Commons integration programme which explored the viability of exporting data from two of these systems as RO-Crate packages with data and contextual metadata. Heurist and OHRM are two Australian software developments which were started before the advent of standardised Linked Data. These systems contain data assets (typically

³ The Biodiversity Heritage Library has using Wikidata to provide stable referencable with PIDS, eg: <https://diff.wikimedia.org/2023/02/14/the-biodiversity-heritage-library-is-round-tripping-persistent-identifiers-with-the-wikidata-query-service/>

documents and photographs) and rich, linked, contextual metadata which not only describes the data, but often represents historical or contemporary domains of study (a city, or a historical period for example).

Initial results from the integration projects were encouraging – in both projects data was successfully exported from being ‘baked in’ to a vertical application stack into interoperable Linked Data “Node graphs as a research output” as McCrabb puts it.

It is worth noting that this export process would be significantly more complex from generic CMS product like WordPress and Drupal as these are very often used with a plethora of plugins and ad-hoc node types and node relationships, in some cases making them similar to bespoke database applications, while the Omeka products are significantly more standardised in that they are built on metadata standards, and Omeka-S in particular uses a JSON-LD approach in its API (with some mild idiosyncrasies) and thus better suited to creating scholarly node-graphs.

In contrast to the discussion above about [Emerging best-practice in software development and reuse](#), there are many fewer models for this kind of annotation-based practice. Historically, research projects have created what amounts to self-contained web sites as outputs, posing challenges for IT departments to keep resources live, and very often preventing any reuse of data as it is either not able to be exported, or exports are in obscure formats with limited tooling.

Work needs to be done with research communities in phase 2, to identify:

- What are the requirements and use cases for Node graphs as a research output, and how will results be identified, archived and potentially access-controlled to be made FAIR
- Which software packages (e.g., Omeka) can currently support these workflows (in the context of the principles set out below for FAIR research) and where are the market gaps?

There is also standardisation work to do on the interchange of records and interoperability of node-graphs; the Heurist and OHRM records from the ARDC integration projects are interoperable at a syntactic level, meaning they can be visualised and edited with domain-agnostic RO-Crate based tooling, but they are not interoperable or combinable with each other as they use different ways of representing the same concepts, even at the level of People, ORganizations and Places, but also in their representation of historical events.

Depending on user demand the CDL could include:

- Guidance on choosing FAIR-compatible approaches:
 - Choosing a linked-data CMS which can produce ‘scholarly-quality’ standards-based node-graphs
 - Planning for a project’s end by making sure that data and code has ‘at rest’ versions
 - Tools and strategies for using public IDs for entities (eg people, languages, places) in node-graphs to enable findability and interoperability
- Further development of import and export services for a range of CMS tools
- Further development of RO-Crate-based editors and website building tools, which have demonstrated promise in pilot projects

The following diagram shows an idealised architecture how Node Graphs could be interchanged and archived via re-usable pipelines that interchange data between scholarly node-graph services, building on and abstracting work by Tim Sherratt on exporting [Trove data to Omeka](#) and the the OHRM and Heurist integration projects.

Reproducibility: How did I get here?

The FAIR article quoted above mentions analytical processes:

Analytical workflows, for example, are a critical component of the scholarly ecosystem, and their formal publication is necessary to achieve both transparency and scientific reproducibility.

One key aim of the CDL is to foster, and establish where necessary a research culture in which formal publication of analytical processes is considered business as usual – but to be able to do that, the processes must lend themselves to being described, packaged and published.

An idealised view of a workflow for analytics and annotation workflows shows the major components that need to be in place for sustainable, reusable research processes. The diagram shows that while researchers spend time ‘playing’, exploring, trying and fine-tuning research analytics, the actual analytical code they use – such as a tweaked Jupyter notebook – needs to be deposited into a repository, possibly assigned a DOI etc.

The all-important (green) repository layer underpins reusability and ongoing access to data at the bottom of the diagram. Even for the duration of a PhD study, it is important that stable, auditable data is available so that as the analysis is evolved over time, results can be compared, and have the best possible chance of being recreated after publication.

Idealised view of a FAIR data research workflows "How did I get here?"

There are many extant workflows, widely used in HASS but not by any means limited to HASS disciplines, that remain problematic for reproducibility or re-use of analytical tools in new contexts – as they do not allow a researcher or subsequent re-users of data to answer the question “How did I get here?”.

1. Problematic tools
 - a. Desktop tools: (platforms such as Adobe Air, desktop Java)
 - b. Project websites whether they are content management systems or databases abound – these often use legacy tools built on platforms that are no longer sustainable or server side infrastructure such as ZopeDB, which often flat-out prevents processes from being re-run.
2. Use of GUI interfaces that do not allow saving of complete application state (these could be online or desktop and range in scope from single user to multi-user application which store data within the application).
3. Online or desktop systems that do not allow for data import and export.

4. Naive - poorly designed Notebooks that may not follow best practice (see this paper for a discussion of the problems and a set of guidelines for best-practice notebooks ([Pimentel et al., 2019](#)))

The CDL Architectural Principles

The proposed principles for CDL development outline some more specific refinements of the Access, Adopt, Adapt, Abstract principles discussed above; looking at specific architectural choices.

We have expressed the principles in the style of the [Manifesto for Agile Software Development](#).

We are uncovering better ways of developing infrastructure for FAIR research tools by doing it and helping others do it. Through this work, experience of multiple successes and failures, and following the example of the GLAM Workbench as our centrepiece service we have come to value:

- | | | |
|--|------|---|
| 1. Static “Infrastructure at rest” | over | hosted “restless” systems that require resources, manage and maintain. Eg: |
| a. Static guidance documentation | over | CMS-based websites requiring management |
| b. Interoperable software libraries over | over | containerized software stacks |
| c. Containerized stacks | over | complete ‘baked’ virtualized machines |
| d. Virtualized machines | over | hard-to-run or precariously hosted services (desktop applications or server-based stacks) |
| 2. Separation of data and applications / analytics | over | application dependent or baked-in data |
| 3. Platform flexibility and efficiency | over | dependence on specific environments and manual configuration |

- | | | |
|---|------|--|
| a. Interoperability standards | over | ad hoc or proprietary systems and integrations |
| b. Automated management / update processes | over | Manual processes |
| | | |
| 4. Extracting the “intellectual core” into reusable code (eg libraries) | over | building apps (including notebooks) with key algorithms or approaches embedded |
| | | |
| 5. Open Source code and Open Access guidance documents | over | proprietary and commercial |
| a. Self documenting | over | no or non-standard metadata created manually |
| b. Design for collaboration, extension, and reuse | over | develop stand-alone projects |

We note also that a CDL needs to function in an infrastructure environment that includes well governed Archival Repository infrastructure for ALL objects used in research (data, code and documents) BUT there currently major gaps in this infrastructure:

- Institutional Data Repository coverage in Australia is not universal, and usually does not deal with access control e.g., for data with human participants.
- Generalist repositories (notably Zenodo) ARE available but these are Open Access only and have storage limits.
- Discipline and generalist repository options for Humanities are very limited

This means for the CDL to expand its scope beyond open data at modest scale, it will depend on the HASS and Indigenous Data Commons filling the gaps.

Implementation of the principles

The above principles are intended as a guide for implementing future CDL components; it will be up to CDL project managers to work with stakeholders to negotiate development and implementation pathways that comply with the principles; this may involve helping research communities re-imagine the solutions they think they want (eg add new features to a legacy desktop app, or add annotations to an collection with no pathway to FAIR management) as compliant solutions that do meet the principles and are thus sustainably FAIR.

Data Lab options, NOTES

While this is an architecture document, the CDL is more of an approach than a single service and is far from unique – research communities have devised similar aggregations under many names. We have found it helpful to think of the CDL architecture in terms of a set of ‘settings’, or selections from an ever evolving menu of possible choices.

In this table we look at some of the CDL settings and give examples of some other choices that might be used in other domains / disciplines or come on board for future iterations of the CDL.

NOTE: this table is a collection of notes, rather than a formal part of the CDL architecture itself. It should not be taken as an exhaustive or well-researched survey of lab architectures but is included as a way to capture some of the discussion that has taken place during Phase 1 and in preparation of this architecture document.

Choice / knob	CDL default “setting”	Other options used by other platforms / possibilities for future phases of the CDL
Guidance documents	Landing page on ARDC resource hub (may point onwards to other, richer resources)	Static site (hosted on github pages) CMS - eg R vignettes, R-Universe for R modules

		<p>HSS Commons?</p> <p>Pages hosted within a data providers guidance (e.g., blogs from Trove, API guidance for a specific service etc)</p> <p>Programming Historian</p>
Analysis Language	Python, R	Javascript is a potential candidate used by some data scientists which may become more important in research (it is used in Voyant Tools' Spyral Notebooks)
Runtime Mode/ / Environment	Jupyter Notebook	<p>Plain-old command line scripts</p> <p>Galaxy⁴ – see the Galaxy Lab approach</p> <p>Genome lab –</p> <p>Neurodesk - A common set of command line tools plus desktop tools which can be run locally, on a server or on HPC systems (includes Jupyter as the “glue” to launch everything, rather than the CDL approach of static web pages where <<guidance>> is the gateway.</p> <p>R Studio, Stata</p> <p>Workflow Languages such as Common Workflow Language.</p>

⁴ Galaxy was used in Alveo – the Human Communications Virtual Lab – a NeCTAR project from 2012-14 – this model did not ‘take’ with researchers in the way that the GLAM lab with its notebooks has but it is not clear if this is because a lack of guidance and support or if it was the wrong model.

Repository configuration	Shared standards, scripts, workflows, actions with RO-Crate packaging	Workflow hub, RO-Crates
Execution Environment ⁵	BinderHub ⁶	JupyterLite CWL for workflows – eg workflowhub (bioinformatics) Singularity Murano catalogue (for containerised service) Nectar virtual desktop service for HASS (windows forthcoming, but linux to start)
Libraries	PyPi	CRAN (R) R-universe Anaconda
Data input repositories	Trove (also an aggregator) LDA ⁷	Discipline repositories where they exist eg Atlas of Living Australia
Generalist Open	Zenodo	Dryad

⁵ More work is needed across ALL disciplines on improving re-runnability of code and workflows.

⁶ See (Candela et al., 2023). NOTE: GW Docker images run in Binder, as a Murano app in Nectar cloud, and could be run in virtual desktop without any changes to the image. JupyterLite might require changes to notebooks, but it should be possible in many cases to write notebooks that will run both in Binder and JupyterLite.

⁷ LDA is being used as an example in CDL 1.0 if time allows and the approach is being tested e.g., with the Heurist export integration project.

repositories for small scale data		Figshare OSF (used by Neurodesk) Institutional Data repositories (where available) Humanities Commons ⁸
Code archive repository	Software Heritage / Zenodo	
Data Interoperability	RO-Crate for data inputs and outputs	

Deployment patterns

As noted above the Phase 1 architecture has many diagrams which represent the CDL approach and its implementation of FAIR principles – these will not be repeated here, except to update the future vision, and capture a potential pattern for deployment in Phase 2 subject to demand.

CDL Future Vision

This diagram has been adapted from one that appeared in the Phase 1 Architecture to include [Annotation-based workflows](#) which were not discussed as a separate type of workspace in Phase 1.

⁸ Worth noting that Humanities Commons is [currently updating](#) their repository to use Invenio (which is what runs Zenodo). Interesting blog about their plans here:

Potential Future Community Data Lab Architecture

The Phase 1 architecture groups two of the work packages (SIA and IAW) under “Fixed Term” services, as they are both server-based systems, provided by a commercial partner which will require ongoing maintenance, according to the principles above, this is the less preferred option, that is hosted “restless”

systems that require resources, to manage and maintain are less desirable than Static “Infrastructure at rest”.

These services (which are examples of very common patterns that will be encountered over and over) are not, at present, able to be deployed via “Infrastructure at Rest”. That is published research outcomes that use these services will not be able to be re-run unless the services are in place. Broadly speaking there are two architectural cases here.

1. For analytics tools such as the SIA Stylometry application, the intellectual Core (the algorithms) could be “librified” and re-constituted as re-runnable workflows. This removes the need for ongoing hosting and would make many more algorithms available to researchers for comparison, rather than being limited to what is built into a particular application.
2. For the annotation Node Graphs that are created by the image annotation workbench, work would need to be done on making image uploads and annotations archivable in public and institutional infrastructure so that data remains FAIR compliant after the contracted maintenance period, and potentially on making services such as general purpose image archiving into supported national infrastructure - moving it from the workspace realm to the archival repositories realm.

Ephemeral APIs: Proxies at Rest

Conal Tuohy has proposed and demonstrated another architectural pattern to adapt Trove and other repository services to work with software that already works with HTTP calls and receives data in standard formats. This pattern may be of use in Phase 2, subject to demand.

Transforming Proxy

Implementing this approach presents some challenges for FAIR implementation aligned with the principles above – making sure that input obtained from a proxy particular can be archived, and that a proxy can be revived when needed involves more virtualised computing than a system based on calling libraries in code; if there are use cases in future CDL phases where this architectural pattern is preferred then they will be dealt with.

Diagram Source

[Diagrams for this document](#) are available on github in plantuml source format and SVG.

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